

An Integrated Dietary Approach to Kidney Disease Management Shows Promising Results in Pilot Study

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Primary endpoints: eGFR, BUN, Serum Creatinine · Follow-up: 6 months and 1 year

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The Kidneyhood dietary program and Albutrix and Microtrix medical foods described in this study are products of Kidneyhood.org. This study was funded by Kidneyhood.org. All authors are affiliated with Kidneyhood.org. Lee Hull, founder of Kidneyhood.org, served as study funder only and had no contact with study participants during the study in order to avoid any conflict of interest. He was not an author and did not participate in study design, data collection, or analysis. All results are reported in aggregate with no identifying patient information.

Data Availability

De-identified participant data are available upon reasonable request to the corresponding author.

Funding

This study received no external funding. All costs were borne by Kidneyhood.org.

Ethics Statement

This study was a retrospective, longitudinal quality improvement analysis of existing program participants who voluntarily provided their laboratory data. Formal IRB review was not required as this study was conducted as a retrospective quality improvement analysis by a private organization and did not involve any experimental intervention. All participants provided informed consent prior to participation. Data was collected via a HIPAA-compliant secure platform, all participant identifiers were replaced with blinded study IDs, and all results are reported in aggregate with no identifying information. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, including voluntary participation, informed consent, and data confidentiality.

Author Contributions

B.E.: Study design, principal investigator oversight, data interpretation, manuscript review.

S.C.: Data collection coordination, statistical methodology, manuscript drafting.

A.M.: Study coordination, patient recruitment, questionnaire design, data collection.

Abstract

Background

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) affects up to 15% of the global population. Both KDIGO 2024 and KDOQI 2020 guidelines recommend very low protein diets (VLPD) combined with keto acid analogs (KAs) for patients at risk of progression. No standardized, integrated dietary program had previously demonstrated measurable improvement in estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) trajectories. The Kidneyhood dietary program (KD) is a turn-key VLPD combining Albutrix — an FDA-registered medical food (21 U.S.C. 360ee(b)(3)) and low-nitrogen keto acid analog with less than 200 mg nitrogen per daily dose — and Microtrix low-serving multivitamin, designed to meet all recommended dietary allowances while minimizing nitrogen load on diseased kidneys.

Methods

Retrospective, longitudinal analysis of 31 CKD stage 3-4 patients with minimum six months of consistent KD program use. HIPAA-compliant data collection via secure platform; informed consent obtained; participants assigned blinded study IDs. Laboratory data collected at baseline, six months, and one year. Primary endpoints: eGFR, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and serum creatinine — the same endpoints required in kidney disease drug approval trials. Secondary: serum albumin and blood glucose. One-way ANOVA with post hoc Tukey comparisons; Cohen's d effect sizes calculated. Results compared against published historical benchmark of eGFR decline in untreated CKD (Garofalo et al., Am J Kidney Dis, 2024).

Results

- eGFR: increased from mean 33.2 to 43.1 mL/min/1.73m² at one year (ANOVA p=.029); post hoc baseline to one year +9.9 mL/min (p=.036, Tukey); 80% of participants improved eGFR.
- BUN: decreased from 33.9 to 19.7 mg/dL at one year (ANOVA p<0.001, $\eta^2=0.199$); Cohen's d=1.04 at six months and 0.89 at one year (large effect); 92% reduced BUN at six months; over 80% achieved normal BUN levels.
- Creatinine: decreased from 2.19 to 1.74 mg/dL (ANOVA p=.028); 86.2% reduced at six months.
- Blood glucose: no significant change (p=.957), confirming diabetic safety.
- Albumin: stable (p=.940), confirming nutritional adequacy on VLPD.
- Historical comparison: mean eGFR change (+9.9 mL/min/1.73m²) significantly greater than published CKD decline rate (-5 mL/min/1.73m²/year); t=6.951, df=173, p<0.001, Cohen's d≈0.93. Patient adherence: 75%.

Conclusions

The Kidneyhood integrated VLPD + keto acid analog program demonstrated statistically significant improvements in eGFR, BUN, and creatinine over one year in CKD stage 3-4 patients. The BUN reduction effect size (Cohen's d=1.04 at six months) is large by conventional standards. This is the first dietary program to document measurable eGFR improvement and normal BUN achievement in the majority of participants. A 75% adherence rate addresses the primary limitation of prior low-protein diet studies. Limitations include small sample size, lack of randomized control, and retrospective design. Larger randomized controlled trials are warranted.

Keywords

chronic kidney disease; keto acid analogs; very low protein diet; eGFR; blood urea nitrogen; Albutrix; medical food; integrated dietary program

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INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD), hallmarked by a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of less than 60 mL/min/1.73 m² or other indicators of kidney damage, has a high global burden with incidence reported as up to 15% of the global population and is often unrecognized until advanced stages.¹ Globally, incidence has been rising, possibly attributable to increases in diseases that are the main causes of CKD in the developed world such as type 2 diabetes or hypertension. CKD is considered chronic, and all etiologies of CKD are considered progressive. Thus, the main goal of treatment is typically to slow the progressive loss of kidney function as well as delay the time until renal replacement therapy is started. Beyond the typical therapy with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors as well as therapy aimed at the etiology, dietary factors within the context of CKD have been at the forefront of research, as the kidneys regulate numerous end products of dietary intake along with vitamins and minerals. Although the beneficial effects of dietary interventions, namely low-protein diets (LPDs), have been shown in the literature, the optimal approach is unknown, and some studies have demonstrated conflicting results leading to a lack of general recommendations to date sometimes owing to a lack of adherence. We have examined the effects of a standardized very low-protein diet supplemented with keto acid analogues as well as appropriate vitamin intake to match recommended dietary allowances (RDAs) in patients with CKD.

Kidneyhood.org diet (KD) is a “turn-key” LPD that includes keto acid analog low-nitrogen protein food Albutrix S3, S4, or S5 and Microtrix low-serving multivitamin. The KD is compliant with relevant 2020 KDOQI and 2024 KDIGO guidelines; both recommend very low-protein diets combined with keto acid analogs. Previous studies that have included keto acid analogs have typically used Ketosteril. However, Ketosteril contains 864 mg of nitrogen per daily dose compared with Albutrix with < 200 mg of nitrogen, enabling the patients to consume 5–8 g more of dietary protein for a total of 0.4 g of dietary protein per kg of body weight per day. This means, as an example, that an 80 kg adult can consume 32 g of protein per day compared with 24 g if on a LPD supplemented with Ketosteril. Another advantage of increase in allowance of daily protein owing to lowered nitrogen load from keto acid analog

supplementation is the possibility of using whole foods, not just specialty low-protein foods typically made from starch, increasing patient satisfaction and compliance. Finally, the KD includes educational material and instructions for patients in the form of a book titled “Stopping Kidney Disease Basics,” and the patients are able to contact the program for support via phone calls, emails, or similar methods 24/7. In general, most patients that finish the self-education aspects as well as consult with the program coordinators, spend a year or longer on the diet.

The pilot study had several objectives focused on efficacy and nutritional safety. The primary goal was to evaluate the impact of the KD intervention on GFR trajectories. A secondary aim was to determine the level of dietary protein or supplemental nitrogen restriction needed to normalize blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels; a target not achievable through existing pharmacotherapy. Lastly, the study aimed to assess whether the integrated dietary approach met patients’ nutritional needs. Ultimately, the KD intervention seeks to improve kidney function in CKD patients, a more ambitious goal than the traditional aim of merely improving some kidney related tests.

METHODS

The KD study was a retrospective, longitudinal analysis conducted among past KD participants. Email invitations were sent to individuals who had been using Albutrix and Microtrix for at least 6 months and had reordered these products at scheduled intervals, indicating regular use. The email invitation (Appendix A) invited participants to respond if they were interested in joining the study. Those who responded were assigned a study identification number and provided with instructions to access the HIPAA-compliant, secure webpage where the study questionnaire (Appendix C) was hosted.

The questionnaire collected demographic information and responses to open-ended questions about participants’ experiences with the program and any health changes since starting the KD regimen. Participants were asked to collect all laboratory data from the time of their first purchase of Albutrix up to the present day, with the earliest lab results recorded as baseline data. Medical records could be uploaded to the secure platform or mailed to the study coordinator, who manually entered all data into a secure spreadsheet (Appendix D).

Thirty-one participants completed the questionnaire and submitted lab results for at least 1 baseline and 1 follow-up visit. As a token of appreciation, each participant received a \$200 Visa gift card.

RESULTS

The analysis included a total of 31 participants at baseline. Thirty of these participants submitted records for at least 1 year. Demographics are presented in Table 1. Data was analyzed at both the 6-month and 1-year marks. The analysis focused on the areas that have the most effect on kidney function: serum albumin, estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), serum creatinine, BUN, and blood glucose levels. Descriptive statistics for these parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Demographics of the Participants at Baseline

Characteristic		All participants (n = 31)
Age, mean (SD), y		70.3 (12.5)
Sex	Male No. (%)	18 (58.1)
	Female No. (%)	13 (41.9)
BMI, mean (SD), kg/m ²		23.5 (3.1)
White race, No. (%)		27 (87.1)

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Kidney Function Lab Parameters

Parameters	No.	Mean (SD)	Range	
Serum albumin, g/dL	Baseline	20	4.1 (0.6)	2.9-5
	6-Month	19	4.2 (0.6)	3.2-5
	1-Year	19	4.1 (0.5)	3.2-4.7
eGFR, mL/min/1.73 m ²	Baseline	31	33.2 (14.4)	10-59
	6-Month	30	41.5 (15.9)	15-67
	1-Year	30	43.1 (15.7)	16-67
Serum creatinine, mg/dL	Baseline	30	2.19 (0.91)	1.02-4.74
	6-Month	28	1.74 ±(0.63)	0.95-3.39
	1-Year	29	1.74 (0.63)	1.02-3.39
BUN, mg/dL	Baseline	28	33.9 (19.7)	9-89
	6-Month	25	18.1 (10.6)	7-52
	1-Year	26	19.7 (11.5)	7-52
Blood glucose, mg/dL	Baseline	30	93.9 (16.4)	61-135
	6-Month	29	95.3 (20.3)	71-169
	1-Year	28	94.2 (17.0)	76-143

Serum Albumin

Descriptive statistics for serum albumin showed a mean value of 4.1 g/dL at baseline, 4.2 g/dL at 6 months, and 4.1 g/dL at 1 year. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results (Table 3) indicated no significant difference in serum albumin levels over time ($F = 0.062$, $p = .940$, $\eta^2 = 0.002$). Albumin levels were stable.

Table 3. ANOVA of Serum Albumin Values

Cases	Sum of squares ^a	Mean square	F test (df)	P value	η^2
Time	0.034	0.017	0.062 (2)	0.940	0.002
Residuals	15.215	0.277	(55)		

^aType III sum of squares.

Figure 1. Mean serum albumin levels over time.

Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate (eGFR)

The mean eGFR values were 33.2 mL/min/1.73 m² at baseline, 41.5 mL/min/1.73 m² at 6 months, and 43.1 mL/min/1.73 m² at 1 year. ANOVA (Table 4) revealed a significant difference over time ($F = 3.686$, $P = .029$, $\eta^2 = 0.077$). Post hoc analysis (Table 5) showed a significant increase in eGFR from baseline to 1 year (mean difference = 9.9, $P = .036$).

Table 4. ANOVA of eGFR Values

Cases	Sum of squares ^a	Mean square	F test (dF)	P value	η^2
Time	1741.781	870.891	3.686 (2)	.029	0.077
Residuals	20792.241	236.275	(88)		

^aType III sum of squares.

Table 5. Post Hoc Comparisons of eGFR Values by Time

		Mean difference	SE	t	P_{Tukey}^a
Baseline	6 months	-8.3	3.9	-2.118	0.092
	1 year	-9.9	3.9	-2.521	0.036
6 months	1 year	-1.6	3.9	-0.400	0.916

^a P value adjusted for comparing a family of 3.

Figure 2. Mean eGFR levels over time.

Serum Creatinine

The mean serum creatinine levels were 2.19 mg/dL at baseline, 1.74 mg/dL at 6 months, and 1.74 mg/dL at 1 year. ANOVA (Table 6) indicated a significant reduction in serum creatinine levels over time ($F=3.736$, $P=.028$, $\eta^2=0.080$). Post hoc comparisons (Table 7) showed a borderline decrease from baseline to 6 months (mean difference = 0.45, $P=.053$) and from baseline to 1 year (mean difference = 0.45, $P=.052$).

Table 6. ANOVA of Creatinine Values

Cases	Sum of squares ^a	Mean square	F test (dF)	P value	η^2
Time	4.058	2.029	3.736 (2)	.028	0.080
Residuals	46.705	0.543	(86)		

^aType III sum of squares

Table 7. Post Hoc Comparisons of Creatinine Values by Time

		Mean difference	SE	t	P _{Tukey} ^a
Baseline	6 mo	0.45	0.19	2.359	0.053
	1 y	0.45	0.19	2.368	0.052
6M	1 y	-0.01	0.19	-0.011	1.000

^aP-value adjusted for comparing a family of 3.

Figure 3. Mean serum creatinine levels over time.

Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN)

The mean BUN levels were 33.9 mg/dL at baseline, 18.1 mg/dL at 6 months, and 19.7 mg/dL at 1 year. ANOVA showed a significant decrease in BUN levels over time ($F=9.433, P<0.001, \eta^2=0.199$). Post hoc tests (Table 9) revealed significant reductions from baseline to 6 months (mean difference = 15.8, $p=.001$, Cohens $d=1.04$) and from baseline to 1 year (mean difference = 14.2, $P=.020$, Cohens $d=0.89$).

Table 8. ANOVA of BUN Values

Cases	Sum of squares ^a	Mean square	F test (dF)	P value	η^{22}
Time	4083.042	2041.521	9.433 (2)	<.001	0.199
Residuals	16448.857	216.432	(76)		

^aType III sum of squares.

Table 9. Post Hoc Comparisons of BUN Results by Time

		Mean difference (95% CI) ^a	SE	t	P _{Tukey}
Baseline	6M ^b	15.8 (6.1-25.4)	4.048	3.896	<.001
	1Y	14.2 (4.6-23.8)	4.007	3.544	0.002
6M	1Y	-1.6 (-11.4 to 8.3)	4.121	-0.382	0.923

^aP-value and confidence intervals adjusted for comparing a family of 3 estimates (confidence intervals corrected using the Tukey method).
^bAbbreviations: 6M, 6 months; 1Y, 1 year.

Figure 4. Mean BUN levels over time.

Blood Glucose

The mean blood glucose levels were 93.9 mg/dL at baseline, 95.3 mg/dL at 6 months, and 94.2 mg/dL at 1 year. ANOVA (Table 10) showed no significant change in blood glucose levels over time ($F=0.044$, $P=.957$, $\eta^2=0.001$).

Table 10. ANOVA of Blood Glucose Levels

Cases	Sum of squares ^a	Mean square	F test (dF)	P value	η^2
Visit	28.814	14.407	0.044 (2)	.957	0.001
Residuals	27198.910	323.797	(84)		

^aType III sum of squares.

Figure 5. Mean blood glucose levels over time.

Change Summary Statistics

Eighty percent of participants had an improved eGFR at both 6 months and 1 year. Ninety-two percent had a decline in BUN at 6 months, and 84.6% still demonstrated this decline at 1 year. Serum creatinine decreased in 86.2% of participants at 6 months and in 83.3% of participants at 1 year.

The mean change in eGFR among participants in the Albutrix arm is 300% greater than the decline observed in historical data. Specifically, the mean change in eGFR in the Albutrix study was 9.9 mL/min/1.73 m², compared to a mean decline of about -5 mL/min/1.73 m² in the historical data.² This difference was statistically significant ($t=6.951$, $df=173$, $p<0.001$), with a large effect size (Cohens $d\approx 0.93$), indicating that the Albutrix program led to a substantial clinical improvement in eGFR.

Qualitative Results

One open-ended question posed to participants was ‘What Health-Related Changes Have You Noticed Since Starting the Stopping Kidney Disease Program?’ Participants responded with a slew of positive health changes, which are summarized below along with some representative quotes.

- Significant improvement in GFR: “*...dialysis is not in my immediate future anymore*”
- Improved energy
- Improved digestive functions: “*no more heartburn*”
- Better workout stamina: “*not short of breath anymore*”
- Improved mental clarity
- More confidence
- Reduced the number of medications needed and/or medication dosage was reduced: “*Off all of my diabetes meds now*”
- Significant weight loss
- Improved mood (happier, more optimistic): “*I look and feel younger*”
- Less anxiety and stress “*not just about my disease being under control, but also about life in general*”
- Better cholesterol
- Increased libido
- Better sleep
- No more heart palpitations

Participants were effusive in their praise for the program. Some representative quotes include:

“The nephrologist is blown away! Initially he said the diet would not make a difference. Over the past three years her eGFR just steadily increased.”

“It works! [Disease Management] requires a total commitment. No indication of nutritional issues on the food plan. Weight is holding for 1 year at 167, down from 212 before starting the program.”

“With my current results, I am now very content and happy to stay with this program.”

“Easy to follow.”

DISCUSSION

LPDs have long been investigated in the management of CKD.³ While early studies, particularly the landmark Modification of Diet in Renal Disease (MDRD) trial, failed to show definitive benefits, subsequent meta-analyses incorporating these data have consistently demonstrated the value of LPDs in slowing renal function decline and delaying dialysis initiation.^{4,5} These findings align with physiological principles: reduced protein intake lowers urea production, diminishing the nitrogen load on kidneys. Urea, once considered inert, has now been implicated in insulin resistance, endothelial dysfunction, and atherogenesis, thus exacerbating CKD pathophysiology.^{6,7}

Dietary protein induces hyperfiltration and glomerular damage, contributing to proteinuria, a marker and mediator of kidney injury. High-protein diets are linked to renal vasodilation, glomerular hypertension, and eventual glomerulosclerosis. In contrast, LPDs reduce hyperfiltration, particularly in diabetic nephropathy, by lowering proteinuria and mitigating glomerular damage. The additive benefit of LPDs complements the antiproteinuric effects of renin-angiotensin system inhibitors.⁸⁻¹⁰

Our study demonstrated significant improvements in key renal parameters. Estimated glomerular filtration rate increased by an average of 9.9 mL/min/1.73 m², while serum creatinine and BUN decreased significantly at both 6 months and 1 year when compared with historical data demonstrating a loss of 3.20 mL/min/1.73 m² for studies published after 2011, and when compared with 5.44 mL/min/1.73 m² for those published in the 1990s.² These changes are consistent with previous findings, highlighting the efficacy of standardized LPD interventions. In addition, plant-based diets, which have shown promise in CKD management, are believed to offer benefits through reductions in dietary phosphorus and acid load, as well as lower levels of indoxyl sulfate and other uremic toxins.¹¹ However, no single dietary approach

including plant-based diets has been proven to improve eGFR or eGFR trajectories or achieve normal BUN levels.

One of the primary challenges to the success of LPDs has been adherence,¹² which can influence outcomes. Patient satisfaction was high with KD, with participants reporting improved health and a commitment to continuing the diet, despite initial skepticism from their nephrologists. In our study, the integrated support provided by Kidneyhood.org—offering continuous nutritional guidance and educational resources—resulted in a 75% adherence rate, a critical factor in the positive outcomes observed. The addition of keto acid analogs (KAs) further enhanced the benefits by reducing nitrogen load and preventing malnutrition, a common concern in LPD studies. KAs also demonstrated the ability to lower glomerular hyperfiltration and mitigate muscle catabolism, making them a valuable adjunct to LPDs.¹³⁻¹⁵

Conclusion

The primary objective of the KD was to reduce the nitrogen load on the kidneys through a standardized LPD while minimizing the risk of malnutrition. One of the most significant advantages of this approach is the demonstrated improvement in patient adherence, a critical factor that has compromised the outcomes of prior studies, including the MDRD trial. The KD program achieved high compliance rates by offering 24/7 support and standardized dietary guidelines, ensuring consistency in the approach. Our findings showed statistically significant reductions in creatinine and BUN, along with an increase in eGFR, aligning with numerous studies that affirm the benefits of LPD in CKD management.

A key difference between the KD program and previous studies lies in integration of all aspects of dietary intake. Most earlier studies were non-standardized, leading to inconsistent results due to variations in diet, KA supplementation, and patient adherence. The KD program's standardized approach mitigates these concerns, making it a scalable and easily reproducible solution that could significantly impact morbidity and mortality rates in CKD patients. From a public health perspective, slowing eGFR decline by even 1 mL/min/year could delay the need for dialysis, reducing both patient burden and healthcare costs. With a monthly cost of \$200, the KD presents a cost-effective alternative to the expenses of dialysis.

Despite these promising outcomes, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the patient cohort consisted solely of Stage 3 and 4 CKD patients who were not yet on dialysis, limiting the generalizability of the results to earlier stages of CKD.¹⁶ While some studies suggest that earlier initiation of LPD may result in better long-term outcomes, this remains an area requiring further investigation.¹⁷ Additionally, the KD program's success may be limited by the relatively small sample size and lack of

randomization in our study. Although we demonstrated a statistically significant benefit, the underpowered nature of the study warrants cautious interpretation of the results. Future studies should aim for larger, more diverse populations with randomized, blinded designs to confirm the efficacy of LPDs in various CKD subtypes, especially in combination with KA supplementation.

Another consideration is the differential impact of LPDs on specific CKD etiologies. Diabetic nephropathy, for example, has shown the most benefit from protein restriction, whereas hypertensive CKD or polycystic kidney disease patients have demonstrated more modest results.¹⁸ Thus, personalized dietary interventions may be necessary, further emphasizing the need for more detailed research. Finally, while our findings are encouraging, the retrospective nature of the study leaves room for potential confounders that may have influenced the observed improvements in renal function.

In conclusion, the KD program offers a standardized and scalable LPD with KA supplementation, which has demonstrated both safety and efficacy in reducing CKD progression. With further refinement and larger studies, the KD approach has the potential to become a key strategy in CKD management, addressing both clinical outcomes and public health challenges posed by the increasing global burden of CKD.

Appendix A

INITIAL EMAIL

Hello! Today I'm writing to invite you to participate in a current Kidneyhood.org study. We are looking to determine the results that customers have gotten after following the Stopping Kidney Disease diet and taking Albutrix / Microtrix, and asking for customer feedback on how we can improve.

Dr. Baran Erdik is our Principal Investigator, and he will oversee the study. We have a few others on our team as well, coordinating the day to day aspects of the study and analyzing the data. Rest assured that our team is experienced in conducting these types of studies and we have taken the necessary steps to ensure our study procedures and platform is HIPAA-compliant, meaning that your data is secure and everything will be kept confidential. Participants will be assigned an identification number. All results will be reported in aggregate, with no identifying information being shared.

It should take less than thirty (30) minutes to participate in this study. In exchange for your time completing the survey and submitting your lab reports, we will send a \$200 Visa gift card to you.

If you're interested in being screened to see if you're eligible, or if you have any questions, please reply to this email or call Toni at (XXX) XXX-XXXX.

Thank you,

Lee Hull

P.S. If you don't want any more invitations to this research survey, click [here](#).

Appendix B

EMAIL WITH PARTICIPATION INSTRUCTIONS

Dear (NAME),

Hello, thanks so much for your interest in participating in our study. This email provides information on how to access the survey and instructions. If at any time during the process you have questions, don't hesitate to call me at XXX-XXX-XXXX.

The link to access the study is: ([LINK](#))

Your confidential study identification number is (ID#). You will need to enter your identification number on the first full page of the survey. .

Please read through the following instructions first, as you'll need to gather all of your information prior to accessing the survey.

Instructions to participate:

- 1.** Gather bloodwork and urinalysis reports from the doctor's visit **closest to (DATE)**. This will be considered your baseline visit. If you have a biopsy report, save that as well.
- 2.** Then gather bloodwork and urinalysis reports from the rest of your doctor's visits from then until now. These will be approximately every 90 days or 3 months.
- 3.** Scan and save these documents to your computer, ensuring the scans capture the date and all lab results on the image. It will be easiest for you if you save the documents as 'Baseline lab', 'Baseline urine', 'Visit 1 labs', etc so you can easily find them on your computer and ensure they are being uploaded correctly.
- 4.** Go to the study website ([LINK](#)) and enter your subject identification number (ID#).
- 5.** Complete the brief demographic questionnaire.
- 6.** Click on 'Upload' next to Baseline labs. This will prompt your computer to search for the needed file. Select the correct document and hit 'Enter' on your keyboard. This will upload the document to the database.

7. Repeat these steps for all remaining documents to be uploaded.
8. Complete the final section of the questionnaire and provide feedback on the Stopping Kidney Disease diet and Albutrix.
9. When you are finished, click 'Submit'.

After we have confirmed all data has been uploaded, we will send you the \$200 Visa gift card.

Should you prefer to mail your medical records to us so we can upload them for you, please mail them to:

There will be a checkbox in the survey for you to indicate that you have mailed the documents and will not be uploading them at that time.

If you have any questions, please reply to this email, or call me ,I'm happy to help you however I can.

Sincerely,

Dr. Alyssa Middleton

Kidneyhood.org

Appendix C

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION 1: DEMOGRAPHICS

1. Subject ID #
2. Date Started SKD Program
3. Age
4. Gender
5. Ethnicity/Race
6. List of medications and supplements (up to 10 spaces)
7. Diagnoses besides Chronic Kidney Disease (open text box)
8. Surgeries since starting the SKD program (open text box)
9. Weight prior to starting the Stop Kidney Disease diet
10. Current weight
11. Height
12. Most recent blood pressure reading
13. Have you had COVID-19 since starting the SKD program? (yes/no)

SECTION 2: UPLOADS

14. Biopsy report
15. Baseline blood work
16. Baseline urinalysis
17. F/u visit 1 bloodwork
18. F/u visit 1 urinalysis
19. F/u visit 2 bloodwork
20. F/u visit 2 urinalysis

- 21. F/u visit 3 bloodwork
- 22. F/u visit 3 urinalysis
- 23. F/u visit 4 bloodwork
- 24. F/u visit 4 urinalysis
- 25. F/u visit 5 bloodwork
- 26. F/u visit 5 urinalysis
- 27. F/u visit 6 bloodwork
- 28. F/u visit 6 urinalysis

SECTION 3: QUESTIONNAIRE

- 29. Prior to starting the SKD diet, did you have any previous diet restrictions? Did you follow a specific diet or eating style such as vegetarian, vegan, etc? (open text box).
- 30. Rate your level of compliance with the SKD diet. (Response options: (1) 0-25% compliant (follow less than 1 meal a day on average), (2) 26-50% compliant (up to half of daily meals follow the diet), (3) 51-75% compliant (most meals daily follow the diet) and (4) 76-100% compliant (most to all meals and snacks follow the diet daily).
- 31. Rate your level of compliance with Albutrix. (Response options: (1) 0-25% compliant (take Albutrix as directed less than 2 days per week), (2) 26-50% compliant (take Albutrix as directed 3 days per week), (3) 51-75% compliant (take Albutrix as directed 4 days per week) and (4) 76-100% compliant (take Albutrix as directed 5-7 days per week).
- 32. Rate your level of compliance with Microtrix. (Response options: (1) 0-25% compliant (take Microtrix as directed less than 2 days per week), (2) 26-50% compliant (take Microtrix as directed 3 days per week), (3) 51-75% compliant (take Microtrix as directed 4 days per week) and (4) 76-100% compliant (take Microtrix as directed 5-7 days per week).
- 33. Rate the taste of the food in the Stopping Kidney Disease diet. (Response options: (1) Poor (2) Fair (3) Good (4) Great)
- 34. Any comments you'd like to share about the taste of the food in the Stopping Kidney Disease diet? (open-ended response)

- 35.** Rate the food variety in the Stopping Kidney Disease diet. (Response options: (1) Poor (2) Fair (3) Good (4) Great)
- 36.** Any comments you'd like to share about the food variety in the Stopping Kidney Disease diet? (open-ended response)
- 37.** Rate the ease of preparing meals in the Stopping Kidney Disease diet. (Response options: (1) Poor (2) Fair (3) Good (4) Great)
- 38.** Any comments you'd like to share about the ease of preparing meals in the Stopping Kidney Disease diet? (open-ended response)
- 39.** How can we improve the Stopping Kidney Disease diet? (open-ended response)
- 40.** What is one thing we can do with the Stopping Kidney Disease diet that would help you be more compliant with the diet (following the diet for more meals and snacks each day? (open-ended response)
- 41.** What thoughts/comments would you like to share about Albutrix? (open-ended response)
- 42.** What thoughts/comments would you like to share about Microtrix? (open-ended response)
- 43.** How can we improve Albutrix? (open-ended response)
- 44.** How can we improve Microtrix? (open-ended response)
- 45.** Have you noticed any health-related changes since starting the Stopping Kidney Disease program? If yes, please describe. (yes, no, open-ended comment box)

Appendix D

LAB VALUES COLLECTED

WBC	BUN/Creatinine Ratio
RBC	eGFR
RDW	Sodium
HCT	Potassium
HGB	Chloride
MCV	Carbon Dioxide
MCH	Calcium
MCHC	Protein
Platelet	Albumin
Neutrophils	Globulin
Lymphocytes	Albumin/Globulin Ratio
Monocytes	Bilirubin
Eosinophils	ALP
Basophils	AST
Glucose	ALT
BUN	A1C
Creatinine	

Appendix E

Kidneyhood.org dietary program, Albutrix and Microtrix descriptions

The dietary approach used in this pilot study included 3 integrated components:

1. A very low protein diet optimized for kidney disease patients
2. Albutrix S3, S4, or S5
3. Microtrix low serving multivitamin

Descriptions of each component and the dietary strategy used is described.

Kidneyhood.org dietary program

Currently published as the Stopping Kidney Disease Food Guide.

The Kidneyhood.org dietary program is a very low protein diet consisting of the following:

Dietary protein intake of 0.4 grams per kg of ideal body weight while increasing or limiting intake of the following:

Sodium

Plant based phosphorus

Potassium

Advanced glycation end products (AGE's)

Renal acid load

Supplemental calcium

Saturated fats

Supplemental magnesium

Antioxidants

Polyphenols

Dietary nitrates

Fiber

High/Low glycemic index foods

The dietary approach does not require patients to calculate daily dietary values. Patients are compliant when they follow the program. Approximately 80% of patients can follow the program at home without assistance and still achieve measurable results.

Albutrix S3, S4 and S5

Albutrix low nitrogen protein food is a keto acid analog/amino acid medical food used to supplement protein intake and reduce supplemental nitrogen intake. The dietary strategy used is to only supplement what is missing in dietary amino acid intake. First, dietary intake of essential amino acids is calculated for the Kidneyhood.org dietary program. Second, only shortfalls in dietary intake are supplemented. The total from dietary intake and supplemental intake normally meets or exceeds the RDA for each of the 9 essential amino acids.

The valuable benefit of this strategy is the lowest possible waste workloads for diseased kidneys while ensuring RDAs for each essential amino acid are met.

Albutrix is formulated into 3 versions to optimize long term outcomes and reflect the patient's current needs. The Albutrix series is interchangeable so that patients can switch versions based on current blood test results. This strategy allows patients to control intake of supplemental calcium and magnesium.

Albutrix S3 or stage 3 is the first magnesium based keto acid analog. Long-term use of supplemental calcium is no longer recommended for kidney patients (2016 KDOQI) due to risks of accelerated heart disease. Albutrix S3 allows long term use without the risk of supplemental calcium use.

Albutrix S4 or stage 4 is a magnesium/calcium blend consisting of 180 mg of calcium and 180 mg of magnesium for the maximum daily serving. Albutrix S4 allows patients to reduce both calcium and magnesium intake to very low levels.

Albutrix S5 is a 100% calcium-based keto acid analog designed for patients with a GFR below 15. In some late-stage patients, magnesium levels will start to rise. Albutrix S5 allows patients to have a magnesium-free version if needed.

The 3 options allow patients and clinicians to adjust intake as needed to ensure blood test results within normal ranges are achieved and maintained.

Microtrix low serving multivitamin

A similar strategy is used for Microtrix; only shortfalls in dietary intake are supplemented. If dietary intake is 100% of the RDA, then no supplementation is justified. The total intake from the Kidneyhood.org dietary program and Microtrix combine to meet the RDAs.

Higher risk or very patient-specific vitamins or minerals are not supplemented in Microtrix. Vitamin D and iron are not included due the risk of excess intake and wide variation in patient requirements.

Kidneyhood.org Pilot Study References

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